

Mechanism of Self-sensitised Photooxidation of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] by Singlet Oxygen

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The self-sensitised photooxidation of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] (where, TSA is dianion of thiosalicylic acid) in dimethylformamide has been studied. This photooxidation reaction involves the participation of singlet oxygen and its presence has been demonstrated by sodium azide quenching of the reaction. The involvement of singlet oxygen in the above reaction has been further supported by kinetic studies of photooxidation of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)]. The self-sensitised photooxidation of the platinum complex is also compared with bilirubin and has been found to be similar.

RECENTLY the photooxidation of [Pt(dipy)(DMT)] (where, DMT is dianion of 3,4-dimercaptotoluene) in CHCl_3 solution has been reported¹. The primary step of this reaction involves an electron transfer from dithiolate ligand of the complex to CHCl_3 molecule. [Pt(dipy)(DMT)] and related complexes have also been shown to form singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$) by energy transfer from triplet excited states of the complexes to triplet oxygen ($^3\text{O}_2$)^{2,3}. [Pt(dipy)(DMT)] has also undergone self-sensitised photooxidation. In this paper, we report the self-sensitised photooxidation studies of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] complex.

Experimental

Potassium tetrachloroplatinate (K_2PtCl_4) and 2,2'-dipyridine (dipy) and thiosalicylic acid were of Strem (U.S.A.), SISCO (India) and B.D.H. (England), respectively. The solvents (reagent grade) were purified before use by the standard methods⁴. Other chemicals used were of A.R. grade and used as such.

[Pt(dipy) Cl_2] was prepared by following the method given elsewhere⁵. [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] was synthesised by the literature method⁶.

Photochemical measurements: A stabilised beam of light from 200 W \times 24 V tungsten-halogen lamp operating at 22 V was directed through a dichroic heat filter having range of transmission between 400 and 710 nm. The filter was placed 14 cm from the light source and the filtered light coming out was directed through a solid clear cast acrylic cylinder (16 \times 4 cm) placed 45 cm from light source. A stoppered 1 cm path-length quartz cuvette having solution of the complex in dimethylformamide was placed on the other side of the cylinder. The course of photolysis was followed by difference absorption spectroscopy in the visible region⁷. The electronic absorption spectra of the complex were recorded on a Varian Superscan-3 uv-visible spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The oxygen-saturated solution of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] in dimethylformamide was chemically affected by light irradiation between 400 and 710 nm due to self-sensitised photooxidation of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)]. The course of this photolysis was followed by difference absorption spectrophotometry in the visible region. The difference absorption spectra of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] in dimethylformamide at different irradiation times in presence of molecular oxygen are shown in Fig. 1. In presence of sodium azide, the reaction was retarded by 90% (Fig. 1). The absorption spectra of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] in dimethylformamide before irradiation and after all the complex has been converted into its product(s) as a result of photolysis, are given in Fig. 2. Since [Pt(dipy)(CAT)] and Pt(dipy)(BCAT)] (where, CAT and BCAT are dianions of catechol and 4-tert-butylcatechol, respectively) are not photooxidised even after irradiation for 5 h in presence of molecular oxygen⁸, it suggests that 2,2'-dipyridine molecule of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] is not photooxidised. The other possibility left is the photooxidation of sulphur of thiosalicylic acid molecule of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)]. The spectrum of photooxidised product of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] compares favourably with the spectrum of [Pt(dipy)(PTA)] (where, PTA is dianion of phthalic acid), thus, it seems that the sulphur atom of thiosalicylic acid is possibly photooxidised to sulphonate group⁷. Similarly, one sulphur of 3,4-dimercaptotoluene in [Pt(dipy)(DMT)] was photooxidised to sulphonate group as reported earlier⁹. The solution was found quite stable when either molecular oxygen saturated solution of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] was kept in dark or irradiated with light while molecular nitrogen was bubbled through it. This confirms that both light and molecular oxygen are necessary to induce the above reaction. The quenching of above reaction in presence of sodium azide suggests the involvement of singlet oxygen⁸. Further, the above results suggest that the observed decay of

Fig. 1. Difference uv-visible spectra of DMF solution of $[Pt(dipy)(TSA)]$ ($200 \mu M$) (—) at different times of light irradiation and at 30 minutes of irradiation (---) in presence of sodium azide ($500 \mu M$) with light of wavelengths between 400 and 710 nm.

Fig. 2. Uv-visible spectra of $[Pt(dipy)(TSA)]$ ($200 \mu M$) before light irradiation (—) and after light irradiation (---) when all of $[Pt(dipy)(TSA)]$ has been converted into its photoproducts.

[Pt(dipy)(TSA)] is due to self-sensitised photooxidation involving singlet oxygen.

A linear plot is obtained by plotting logarithms of concentration monitored at 496 nm *versus* times of photolysis as shown in Fig. 3. This suggests a first order kinetics for self-sensitised photooxidation of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)]. This is very similar to self-sensitised photooxidation of [Pt(dipy)(DMT)] as

Fig. 3. Plot of log of concentration against time of light irradiation of DMF solution of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] (200 μ M) with light of wavelengths between 400 and 700 nm.

reported earlier³. Thus, the following mechanism is proposed to explain the above kinetics for self-sensitised photooxidation of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)]⁶,

and

where, 1S_0 , 1S_1 and 3S_1 are ground state, first excited singlet state and first triplet state of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)], respectively, ISC is inter-system crossing,

ET is energy transfer, k_d is rate constant of 1O_2 decay in dimethylformamide solvent molecules, k_q is rate constant of physical quenching of 1O_2 by [Pt(dipy)(TSA)], and k_r is rate constant of chemical quenching of 1O_2 by [Pt(dipy)(TSA)].

Production of 1O_2 by energy transfer from [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] is given by equation (1)¹⁰,

$$\frac{d[{}^1O_2]}{dt} = I_{ab}\phi_{{}^1O_2} \quad (1)$$

where, $\phi_{{}^1O_2}$ is quantum yield of 1O_2 formation and I_{ab} is the intensity of absorbed light. Photooxidation of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] involves the concentration change of the complex which is given by

$$\frac{-d[S]}{dt} = k_r[{}^1O_2][S] \quad (2)$$

Under steady state condition, based on the above scheme,

$$\frac{-d[S]}{dt} = I_{ab}\phi_{{}^1O_2} \frac{k_r[S]}{\{k_r[S] + k_q[S] + k_d\}} \quad (3)$$

when, $k_d \gg (k_q + k_r)[S]$, equation (5) reduced to

$$\frac{d[S]}{dt} = -I_{ab}\phi_{{}^1O_2} \left(\frac{k_r}{k_d} \right) [S]$$

$$\text{and } \log[S] = -kt + c \quad (4)$$

where, $k = I_{ab}\phi_{{}^1O_2} \frac{k_r}{k_d}$.

If a decay of S is carried out, a plot of $\log[S]$ *versus* different times of irradiation is expected to be a straight line with a slope of k provided I_{ab} , solvent, sensitizer concentration and acceptor concentration are the same. Since S acts both as sensitizer and acceptor of 1O_2 , a linear plot of $\log[S]$ *versus* time is expected to be observed only for the initial stages of disappearance of S during which time average sensitizer concentration is nearly constant. Indeed the observed linear plot in Fig. 3 supports the above mechanism involving singlet oxygen. Reaction is slow, so < 15% sensitizer is only oxidised in 30 min. After 30 min the non-linearity in plot is obtained.

The self-sensitised photooxidation of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] is also compared with self-sensitised photooxidation of [Pt(dipy)(DMT)] and bilirubin. The bilirubin is well known sensitizer of singlet oxygen, which also undergoes a self-sensitised photooxidation⁶. The percentage decrease in absorbance *versus* time for solutions of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)], [Pt(dipy)(DMT)]³ and bilirubin⁶ in dimethylformamide during different times of light irradiation with light of wavelength between 400 to 710 nm were measured under identical conditions. The photooxidation times required for the loss of 30% absorption of [Pt(dipy)(TSA)], [Pt(dipy)(DMT)] and bilirubin were obtained from the plots of percentage decrease in absorbance *versus* time and they are 15, 5 and 7 min, respectively. These data suggest that [Pt(dipy)(TSA)] is equally good sensitizers of singlet oxygen as compared to [Pt(dipy)(DMT)] and bilirubin.

The self-sensitised photooxidation of [Pt(dipy)-(TSA)] involves the singlet oxygen.

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